

Corporate Governance in Axis Bank Limited

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Abstract:

Axis Bank Ltd. Provides corporate and retail banking products and services. The company's products include saving accounts; fixed deposits, recurring deposits; home loans, car loans, personal loan, and loans against shares, property and security; credit cards, debit cards and prepaid cards; forex, investments in mutual fund, demat account, online trading; insurance in health, home, travel, life and other services of prepaid mobile charging, online shopping, locker and e-statement. The company operates through four segments: Treasury, Retail Banking, Corporate/Wholesale Banking and Other Banking Business. The Treasury segment operations include investments in sovereign and corporate debt, equity and mutual funds, trading operations, derivative trading and foreign exchange operations on the proprietary account and for customers and central funding. The Retail Banking segment constitutes lending to individuals/small businesses subject to the orientation, product and granularity criterion and also includes low value individual exposures not exceeding the threshold limit. The Retail Banking activities also include liability products, card services, internet banking, ATM services, depository, financial advisory services and NRI services. The Corporate/Wholesale Banking segment includes corporate relationships not included under Retail Banking, corporate advisory services, placements and syndication, management of public issue, project appraisals, capital market related services and cash management services. The Other Banking Business segment includes para banking activities like third party product distribution and other banking transactions. It also provides services to personal, corporate, NRI's, agricultural and rural markets which are engaged in agricultural business, microfinance, financial inclusion and rural banking. Axis Bank was founded on December 3, 1993 and is headquartered in Mumbai, India. Corporate governance is the system of rules, practices and processes by which a company is directed and controlled. Corporate Governance refers to the way in which companies are governed and to what purpose. It identifies who has power and accountability, and who makes decisions. Corporate governance determines the allocation of authority and responsibilities by which the business and affairs of a bank are carried out by its board and senior management. Accountability transparency and equality of treatment for all stakeholders is the control tenets behind Axis Bank corporate governance philosophy and Axis Bank continually Undertake measures to adopt best practices in corporate governance.

Keywords : Axis bank, stakeholders, Board of directors, corporate governance

Introduction:

Axis Bank Limited is the third largest private sector bank in India, It offers financial services to customer segments covering Large and Mid Sized Corporate, Agriculture, and retail businesses the bank aims to increase its share in the financial services sector by continuing to build a strong retail franchise, corporate governance is a concept which is gaining popularity and is a probably going to be added in the new companies bill as mandatory. It reduces dependency on the government for social change. Corporate Governance is the system by which corporations are directed and controlled. The governance structure specifies the distribution of rights and responsibilities among different participants in the corporation (such as the board of directors, managers, shareholders, creditors, auditors, regulators, and other stakeholders) and specifies the rules and procedures for making decisions in corporate affairs. Governance provides the structure through which corporations set and pursue their objectives while reflecting the context of the social, regulatory, and market environment. Governance is for monitoring the actions, policies, and decisions of corporations. Governance involves the alignment of

interests among the stakeholders. Axis Bank has to play a very important role in the future banking scenario, not in a traditional way but in the way the regulators expect the sectors to function. In all areas of functioning will go a long way in strengthening the fabric of the sector. It is, therefore, necessary that all Axis Bank Employees practice corporate governance continuously to remain a vibrant banking institution and play the role effectively, especially in the area of financial inclusion and micro-level credit dispensation.

Objectives of the study:

The Objectives of the study are :

1. To find out the relevance of practicing corporate governance in Axis Bank.
2. To find out the major parameters of sound corporate governance practices in the Axis Banks.

Research Methodology:

The researcher attempted to study and find out the areas of sound corporate governance practices so that the bank can create a better environment to help the operating management enhance stakeholder value and gain high customer satisfaction. The study has been descriptive and analytical based on the survey method. The primary

data was collected from the different types of customers (salaries and businessmen) in the level of various parameters adopted by the banks for good corporate governance for the assessment of the level of customer satisfaction.

Directors managers and other bank officers were also interviewed to find out the extent of the practice of corporate governance in the bank. A suitable questionnaire was designed and administered to collect responses from the customers. Some 50 respondents, across 5 branches from Jodhpur district have been selected for the study the primary data collected from the respondents of various Axis Banks were analyzed.

Relevance of Corporate Governance in Axis Banks:

Corporate governance covers a variety of aspects such as the protection of shareholders' rights, enhancing the shareholder's value, issues concerning and role of the Board of Directors, deciding the disclosure requirements, prescribing the accounting systems, putting in place effective monitoring mechanisms, etc.

Axis Bank being part of the Indian banking industries, Axis Bank began its operations in 1994,

after the Governance of India allowed new private banks to be established. Axis Bank (Erstwhile UTI Bank) opened its registered office in Ahmedabad and Corporate office in Mumbai in December 1993. The first branch was inaugurated on 2 April 1994 in Ahmedabad by at Finance Minister of India. During 2023, Axis Bank opened 903 branches, The principal objective was to create a development financial for providing medium- term project and long-term project financing to Indian businesses. It is, therefore, a corporate entity. Corporate applies to Axis Banks also since they are considered corporate entities. Corporate governance in banks including Axis Bank is mainly about how banks must set corporate objectives including generating economic returns for the owners, running day-to-day operations of the business, balancing the interests of all the stakeholders with the highest priority, and emphasis on protecting the interest of depositors and align corporate activities and behaviors with applicable laws and regulations. The common thread in most of these cases would be managing and minimizing risk in financial intermediation which is the main function of the bank.

Table 1: Profile of Axis Banks as of the end of March 2014(amount in crores)

YEAR	TOTAL ASSETS	NET PROFIT
March 2021-22	1,175,429	13,025
March 2022-23	1,317,326	21,933

Source: Financial report of Axis BANK

Corporate governance is most relevant today for Axis Bank due to many factors like

- A lot Of scams in Axis Bank have eroded the trust among customers and stakeholders.
- Intense competition from other public a private sector banks and foreign banks is constantly increasing.
- Risks are manifold in today's technology-oriented and customer-driven banking which are posing greater challenges to Axis Bank.
- The competitive edge of Axis Bank is on the decline due to open market banking in a globalized atmosphere.
- Most Axis Banks are in a critical transition for growth and diversification, and if they don't address the major problems properly and professionally, they may have to exit from the sector.

The above factors are not exhaustive but indicative, which are posing multiple challenges to their existence, survival growth, and prosperity. Among many measures adoption of corporate governance can enable the Axis Bank to bring success in its work.

Principals of Corporate Governance:

- Rights and equitable treatment of shareholders: Organizations should respect the rights of

shareholders and help shareholders to exercise those rights. They can help shareholders exercise their rights by openly and effectively communicating information and by encouraging shareholders to participate in general meetings.

- Interests of other stakeholders: Organizations should recognize that they have legal, contractual, social, and market-driven obligations to non-shareholder stakeholders, including employees, investors, creditors, suppliers local communities, customers, and policymakers.
- Role and responsibilities of the board: The board needs sufficient relevant skills and understanding to revise and challenge management performance. It also needs adequate size and appropriate levels of independence and commitment.
- Integrity and ethical behavior: Integrity should be a fundamental requirement in choosing corporate officers and board members. Organizations should develop a code of conduct for their directors and executives that promotes ethical and responsible decision making.
- Disclosure and transparency: Organizations

should clarify and make publicity known the roles and responsibilities of the board and management to provide stakeholders with a level of accountability. They should also implement procedures to independently verify and safeguard the integrity of the

company's financial reporting. Disclosure of material matters concerning the organizations should be timely and balanced to ensure that all investors have access to clear, factual information.

Analysis of Data

Table: 2 Practice of good corporate governance in Axis Bank

S.NO.	Parameters	High (%)	Medium (%)	LOW (%)	Total
1	Corporate mission and goals	30	60	10	100
2	Transparency board of direction	30	60	10	100
3	An effective board of direction	40	55	05	100
4	Norms and guidelines	45	45	10	100
5	Audit and vigilance	40	50	10	100
6	Working on special committees	30	50	20	100
7	Risk profile	35	45	20	100
8	Customer relationship management	25	60	15	100
9	Innovative products and services	55	40	05	100
10	Professionalism	50	40	10	100

Source: compiled from the questionnaire Findings

1. It has been found that around 70 percent of customers are highly satisfied with the services provided by Axis Bank.
2. Axis Banks practices very good corporate governance with respect to corporate mission and goals, transparency effective board of directors, and innovative products and services.
3. The management of the bank needs to pay more attention to areas like norms and Guidelines, audit and vigilance, working of special committees, risk profile, and professionalism in the bank.
4. Axis banks needs to practice good corporate governance with respect to customer relationship management this will help the bank to march forward with greater customer satisfaction and sustained growth.
5. In the present scenario Axis banks shall also focus on corporate social responsibility as it gained more importance considering the social issues and other problems plaguing the economy.
6. The business ethics, value system, and code of conduct should be clearly defined and the banks shall take the necessary initiative and steps for its proper implementation.

Conclusion:

Axis Bank can prosper and flourish by way of adopting the company governance practices developed and developed in banking enterprises from time to time. Corporate governance is a dedication to Ethics, integrity accountability, and transparency . to make certain that the best standards are maintained in those components on an

ongoing basis and to offer safeguards to numerous stakeholders (inclusive of shareholders, depositors, and employees) corporate governance is exceptional from each day management i.e. a crew together with the leader government & pinnacle management functionaries supported by the operating staff. Axis Bank shall hold and nourish the best corporate governance feature for the banking state of affairs, not in a traditional manner but within the way the regulators assume the banking scenario to function, the manner the market pressure, and the client's preference for the arena to feature. The adoption of proper company governance practices in all regions of function will pass an extended way in strengthening the material of the sector. The following notion may be useful in strengthening corporate governance in Axis banks.

- There shall be a clean undertaking of obligations and selection Authority,
- incorporating a hierarchy of required approvals from people, committees, and the board of directors.
- The banks want to set up a better mechanism for the interplay and cooperation among the board of directors, managers, and auditors.
- Develop inner manipulation systems, internal and external audit features, chance management features independent of business strains and other checks and balances.
- There will be unique monitoring of chance publicity wherein conflicts of pursuits can be particularly excessive.
- The banks shall observe properly articulated

strategy in opposition to the achievement of the general banking enterprising and the contribution of the people will be measured.

- The banks need to introduce economic and managerial incentives to behave in an appropriate the manner for the senior control and the personnel in the form of Compensations, promotions, and other recognitions.
- There will be the precise go with the flow of records internally and to the general public.

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